

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-CONCEPT AND SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study was designed to examine the relationship between self-concept and Social intelligence among class-IX students of secondary schools of Bhubaneswar municipality of khordha District. The sample for the present study comprised of 100 secondary school students (50 boys and 50 girls) selected by using simple random techniques. The Descriptive Survey method was adopted for the study. Self-Concept Questionnaire by R.K Saraswat (2005) and social intelligence scale by N.K Chhada and Ganesan (1986) were used to collect the data from the sample subject. Mean, Standard deviation, t-test and Pearson's product moment correlation were used to analyze the data. The findings of the study confirm that there exists positive relationship between self-concept and social intelligence among secondary school students. Most secondary school students have an average level of self-concept and social intelligence. There is no significant difference in the level of self-concept and social intelligence with respect to gender variable.

Keywords: *Self-Concept, Social intelligence, Secondary school students.*

INTRODUCTION

Human needs certain shorts of love, care, attention, bonding and affection to live a happy and successful life. He/she must know societal rules, situation accordance behavior and must understand need and situation of other member of the society and behave as expected. A

well adjusted person is the one who moulds himself/herself according to the needs of the society and develops positive attitude towards other fellow members of the society. So, social intelligence is very important for an individual to lead a successful life in the society. Education is primarily concerned with the enhancement of quality of life of students. Through education they attain all needs of life starting from basic needs to social needs. Social needs and social skills are learned by students mostly at secondary education stage. It is the mean time when they try to understand the world around them in a more comprehensive manner. They make new relationships in society, create their own identity in it and try to adjust them in accordance of the society. As they are in the age of adolescence they face many problems in due process due to physiological changes occurring in body.

‘Self-Concept is the product of one’s reflectivity; it is concept of the individual of himself as a physical, social and moral and existing being. It is sum total of the individual’s thoughts and feelings about himself or herself. Self-concept also plays a vital role in our life. It makes a person more confident and enables him/her to have a better understanding about self. The founding stone of self-concept is laid in the adolescence stage. Self Concept is a crucial aspect in personality development, and for that matter in doing any work with any degree of excellence.

Rationale: As Secondary school students belong to adolescence, they undergoes various rapid physical and psychosocial changes. These changes bring a lot of huddles on that stage of life that may impact their attitude, believe, perception and how they accept the society. The adolescent students struggle to develop their individuality while still conforming to societal norms. Rapid urbanization and modernization have exposed them to changes in society. The resultant breakdown in family structure, excessive or minimal control confuses the adolescent students and makes him/her especially vulnerable to maladaptive patterns of thinking and behavior. Students having a good level of adjustment towards society, surrounding and people around them live a socially peaceful and happy life. For better social competence social intelligence plays major role. Also a person’s self-concept makes him more familiar with his ability. It is the thoughts, believes and attitude towards own ability. A person having sound self-concept has a better understanding of self and will possess a good self-confidence. And self-confidence is the boon for success and adjustment. Good level of adjustment develops better social competence in person. So self-concept may have some influence on social intelligence.

Gakhar(2003), Punithavathi(2011), J Anitha and Paramaswari(2017), T. Sikheswari(2014), Parveez and Tariq(2016), K.Murugan(2017), Dambudz(2005), Riftel Un Nise et. Al.(2011) had studied self-concept and academic achievement along with different variables like motivation, achievement motivation, emotional intelligence and personality etc. other researchers such as P. Suravi(2008), Dsouza(2010), Sangeeta and Sumita(2012), Agrawalla(2013), Manju et al(2015), Tauro(2018), Sung Kyung(2011) studied Self-concept with parental style, stress, BMI, emotional maturity and self-esteem etc. Mallhotra(2020), shak(2010) andb Alrajhi (2019) investigated self-Concept alone.

On the other hand Ganadevan(2007) studied SI in relation to socioeconomic status. Hooda(2009) studied relationship between positive psychological health and SI. Rakshanda(2005), Sharma(2019) and Quingen t al(2008) studied SI with psychological variables such as social awareness, academic achievement, achievement motivation, sensitivity, self-esteem and inter-culture communication. Kumara(2010), Sembyan and Vidwanathan(2012), Kaul(2018), Somyasree and Sreenivas(2019) and S G Jee and Singh(2020) conducted special studies on social intelligence basing upon demographic variables. Sharma(2019) studied SI in relation to happiness in relation to well-being, Aminpoor studied happiness and SI. Hassan and Sharma (2019) studied the relationship between social intelligence and self-concept of working and non-working mothers of kashmir division and found there is positive relationship between social intelligence and self-concept and their findings suggested higher the social intelligence, higher will be self-concept.

From above it can be analyzed that self-concept ad social intelligence were studied along number of psychological and demographic variables. A few or no studies are available which try to investigate the relationship between self concept and social intelligence. Hence the researcher undertook the present study to find out the relationship between self-concept and social intelligence among secondary school students.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: The problem of the proposed study stated as :-

“Relationship between self-concept and social intelligence among Secondary School students.”

OPERATIONAL DEFINATIONS

- **Social Intelligence:** - For the present study Social intelligence means human ability of decoding the happenings of the world and responding to it likewise. Social Intelligence is also the capability to act wisely while maintaining human relations. This ability is exclusive to humans and distinguishes us from the rest of beings in the animal kingdom.

- **Self-Concept:-** Self-concept is a system of attitudes towards oneself. It consists of all the perceptions, feelings, attitudes, aspirations and values of oneself concerning oneself. for the proposed study It is represented by the score obtained on Self-Concept Questionnaire (SCQ-S) developed by Dr. Rajat Kumar Saraswat (2005).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Objectives of the present study were:-

1. To find out level of self-concept of secondary school students.
2. To find out level of social intelligence of secondary school students.
3. To compare level of self-concept of boy and girl secondary school students.
4. To compare level of social intelligence of boy and girl secondary school students.
5. To find out relationship between social intelligence and self-concept of secondary school students.

HYPOTHESES

H01: There is no significant difference in level of self-concept boy and girl secondary school students.

H02: There is no significant difference in level of social Intelligence of boy and girl secondary school students.

H03: There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and Self-concept of secondary school students.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY: The present study was limited to Bhubaneswar municipality of khordha District only. This study was limited to class-IX students only. Again the study was limited to 100 secondary school students (50 boys & 50 girls) in its sample size.

METHOD ADOPTED: The investigator adopted 'Descriptive Survey Method' for the study, considering its relevance and feasibility.

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Independent variable: - Self-Concept was taken as dependent variable in the present study.

Dependent variable: - Social Intelligence was taken as independent variable in the study.

SAMPLE: The present study a sample of 100 Secondary School Students of Khordha District was selected by simple random sampling. For the selection of the sample the investigator prepared a list of all Secondary Schools of Bhubaneswar municipality district and selected 10 Schools randomly.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS: In the present study instrument employed for the collection of data with the help of the following tools:

- a) Self Concept Questionnaire by R.K. Saraswat
- b) Social Intelligence Scale by M.K. Chadda and Usha Ganesam

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRITATION: In the present study the researcher had used simple statistical devices like mean standard deviation and percentage to analyze level of self-concept and social intelligence of secondary school students.

Table-1: Mean Score of secondary school students on Self-Concept Questionnaire with respect to gender.

SCORE	GENDER		TOTAL
	BOYS	GIRLS	
MEAN	126.1	123.36	124.73
SD	57.26745	56.89538	57.73745

Fig-1

Table-2: Percentage of secondary school students in different level of self-concept with respect to gender

LEVEL OF SELF-CONCEPT	SCORE RANGE	GENDER				TOTAL	
		BOYS		GIRLS		N	%
		N	%	N	%		
HIGH	171 - 240	14	28	12	24	26	26
AVERAGE	71 - 170	23	46	23	46	46	46
LOW	1 - 70	13	26	15	30	28	28
TOTAL		50	100	50	100	100	100

Fig-2

Analyzed data shown that mean score of secondary school students in self-concept questionnaire is 122.99 which falls in average score range of (71 - 170) of SCQ. Also Out of the total population 46% of secondary school students have average level of score in self-concept questionnaire. In case of social intelligence mean score of secondary school students are 89.08 which is within the average level (67-108) of score range of SIS. Out of total sample 52% of secondary school students have average and level score on SIS.

Table- 3: Mean Score of secondary school students on social intelligence scale with respect to gender of school

SCORE	GENDER		TOYTAL
	BOYS	GIRLS	
MEAN	88.32	89.84	89.08
SD	28.12178	25.90607	25.59107

Fig-3

Table-4: Percentage of secondary school students in different level of social intelligence with respect to gender of school

LEVEL OF SOCIAL INTELIGENCE	SCORE RANGE	GENDER				TOTAL	
		BOYS		GIRLS		N	%
		N	%	N	%		
HIGH	109 - 138	13	26	9	18	22	22
AVERAGE	67 - 108	22	44	30	60	52	52
LOW	1 - 66	15	30	11	22	26	26
TOTAL		50	100	50	100	100	100

Fig-4

Analyzed data showed that 26% of boys and 18% of girls have high level score on SIS. 30% of boy secondary school students and 22% of girl secondary school students have low level of score on SIS. Boys secondary school students have a mean score of 88.32 and 89.84 is the mean score of girls on social intelligence scale. Mean score of total sample is 89.08 on social intelligence scale. It is indicating that secondary school student of both the gender have almost equal and average level of score on SIS.

Table.5: Mean, SD and t-value of self-concept of boys and girls secondary school students

Gender	N	Mean	SD	DF	SE _D	t-Value	significance
Boys	50	126.1	57.2675	98			Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	50	123.36	56.8954				
					9.5829	0.2859	

T test was used for comparison of mean score of self-concept of boys and girl secondary school students and the obtained t-value was 0.2859 which was less than table value of 't' at 0.05 significance level. Hence the null hypothesis was accepted. There is no significant difference in level of self-concept of secondary school students.

Table- 6: Mean, SD and t-value of social intelligence of boys and girls secondary school students

Gender	N	Mean	SD	DF	SE _D	t-Value	significance
Boys	50	88.32	28.1217	98	4.8256	0.3149	Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	50	89.84	25.9060				

Researcher obtained a t-value of 0.3149 when social intelligence score of boy and girl secondary school students were compared. Obtained 't' value is less than table t-value of 't' at 0.05 level of significance so the null hypothesis was accepted. There is no significant difference in level of social intelligence of secondary school students.

Table – 7: r-value of Self-Concept and Social Intelligence of secondary school students

Variable	N	DF	r- Value	Significance
Self-concept	100	98	0.9621	Significant at 0.05 level
Social intelligence	100			

The researcher calculated r-value to know relationship between self-concept and social intelligence by using Pearson product moment correlation. This analysis gave a positive correlation of 0.962. So the null hypothesis was rejected as obtained r-value is more than critical r value at 0.01 level of significance. There exists positive relationship between self-concept and social intelligence of secondary school students.

RESULTS: The following main findings have emerged as an outcome of the present investigation:-

1. It is found that most of the secondary school students have average level of self-concept.
2. Most of the secondary school students have average level of social intelligence.
3. There is no significant difference in level of self-concept of boys and girls secondary school students.

4. There is no significant difference in level of social intelligence of boys and girls secondary school students.

5. There is high positive significant relationship between self-concept and social intelligence of secondary school students.

CONCLUSION: Self-concept has positive influence over social intelligence. So every secondary school must put due effort to enhance level of Self-Concept of secondary school student which will in return increase their performance level. Secondary education curriculum must include activities that will enhance self-concept in learner. Special attention must be paid to the vast majority of the students, studying in secondary schools to develop their Self-Concept. Teacher should perform testing programmes & diagnosis the self-concept through testing identity and remedial programs for the students. Teacher should try to improve self-concept of students by constructing different programs.

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